

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE TVL K-12 CURRICULUM AND THE GRADUATES' EMPLOYABILITY: BASES FOR FLEXIBLE TEACHING LEARNING IN THE NEW NORMAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study is conducted to assess the implementation of the TVL K-12 curriculum and the graduates' employability; thus, its findings aim to serve as bases for flexible teaching learning in the New Normal Education. Specifically, it aimed to answer the (1) profile of the respondents, (2) students' perception of the TVL K-12 curriculum, (3) employability level of TVL graduates in terms of a job waiting time, job promotion, job security, and job satisfaction; (4) significant relationship between TVL K-12 Curriculum component and the Graduates' employability. A quantitative research methodology to assist certain descriptive conclusions and inquiries made possible through a self-made survey questionnaire was used. The 90 respondents are graduates of Pagbilao National High School and are all residents of the municipality of Pagbilao, Quezon. TVL graduates feel comfortable and satisfied in their employment as more companies observe professionalization and equal treatment of workers while also acknowledging the talents and contributions of TVL graduates in the industry. There is a significant relationship between the TVL K-12 curriculum component and the graduates' employability. It is beneficial for educators to focus on how to make teaching and learning as meaningful and successful as in conventional classroom environments. Teachers might consider honing their technological skills, especially in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to effectively adapt to the needs of the new normal education making teaching-learning flexible.

Keywords: TVL K-12 Curriculum, NC2, TVL Graduates' Employability, Job Satisfaction